

ROMAN DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION NUMBER USING AN ALGORITHM OF AN INTERVAL GRAPH

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1.1. ABSTRACT:

A survey on results and applications of dominating sets was presented by E.J. Cockayne and S.T. Hedetniemi[1]. Among the various applications of the theory of domination, the most often discussed is communication network. There has been persistent in the algorithmic aspects of interval graphs in past decades spurred much by their numerous applications of interval graphs corresponding to interval families.

Today graph theory is one of the most flourishing branches of modern mathematics. Graphs are useful in enhancing the understanding of the organization and behavioral characteristics of complex system. The study of domination in graphs originated around 1850 has become the source of interest to the researchers.

Roman domination in graphs is introduced by Cockayne et.al [2,3] and they studied this concept for various graphs. In this paper we find doubly connected dominating set through the algorithm and prove the property of Roman doubly connected domination number.

INDEXED TERMS : Interval graph, Dominating set, Doubly connected dominating set, Roman domination number, Roman doubly connected domination number.

1.2. PRELIMINARIES:

The theory of domination in graphs introduced by Ore [4] and Berge [5] is an emerging area of research in graph theory today. An introduction and an extensive overview on domination in graphs and related topics is surveyed and detailed in the two books by Haynes et.al, [6,7].

Let $I = \{I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, \dots, I_n\}$ be any interval family, where each I_i is an interval on the real line and $I_i = [a_i, b_i]$, for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n$. Here a_i is called the left end point labeling and b_i is the right end point labeling of I_i . Without loss of generality, we assume that all the end points of the intervals in I are distinct numbers between 1 and $2n$. Two intervals i and j are said to be intersect each other if they have non - empty intersection.

A graph $G = (V, E)$ is an interval graph if the vertex set V can be put into one-to-one correspondence with a set of intervals I on the real line R such that two vertices of G are joined by an edge in E if and only if their corresponding intervals in I have non-empty intersection. That is if $i = [a_i, b_i]$ and $j = [a_j, b_j]$, then i and j intersect means either $a_j < b_i$ or $a_i < b_j$. The set I is called an interval representation of G and G is referred to as the intersection graph of I . Also we say that the intervals contain both its end points and that no two intervals share a common end point. The intervals and vertices of an interval graph are one and the same thing. The graph G is connected and the list of sorted end points is given and the intervals in I are indexed by increasing right end points that is $b_1 < b_2 < b_3 < \dots < b_n$.

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. A set $D \subseteq V(G)$ is a dominating set of G if every vertex in V/D is adjacent to some vertex in D . A dominating set D of the graph $G(V, E)$ is a non - split dominating set if the induced subgraph $\langle V - D \rangle$ is connected. A subset $D \subseteq V(G)$ is called dominating set if $N[D] = V(G)$. The minimum cardinality of such a set D is called the domination number $\gamma(G)$ of the graph G . A dominating set D is connected if the subgraph induced by D is connected. The minimum cardinality of connected dominating set D is called the connected dominating number $\gamma_c(G)$ of G . A connected dominating set D is said to be doubly-connected dominating set, if the sub-graph induced by the the set $V-D$ is connected.

The minimum cardinality of such set is called the doubly connected domination number. It is denoted by $\gamma_{cc}(G)$.

$G(V, E)$ is a function $f:V \rightarrow \{0,1,2\}$ satisfying the condition that every vertex u for which $f(u) = 0$ is adjacent to at least one vertex v for which $f(v)=2$. The weight of a Roman dominating function is the value $f(v) = \sum_{v \in V} f(v)$. The minimum weight of a Roman dominating function on a graph G is called as the Roman domination number of G . It is denoted by $\gamma_R(G)$. If $\gamma_R(G) = 2\gamma(G)$ then G is called a Roman graph. Here we introduce the new notation that Roman doubly connected domination number that mean it was the Roman domination of doubly connected dominating set and that domination number was denoted as $\gamma_{DCR}(G)$.

1.3. EXPLANATION OF THE ALGORITHM

For finding the doubly connected domination through an algorithm, we consider a connected interval graph. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a connected interval graph. According to the increasing order we set the intervals. First of all we treat none of a vertex of $V(G)$ is a member of Doubly connected dominating set DCDS. Then insert vertices one by one by testing their consistency. If a vertex v is dominated by at least two vertices, then leave it, otherwise take the second highest numbered adjacent vertex from $N[v]$ as a member of DCDS if it is not adjacent to the next member of $N[v]$ or v is not the last vertex, clearly given in the algorithm of section 1.4.

Let us associate a new term $M_i(v)$, for a vertex $v \in V$, for all $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k (k = |N(v)|)$ to each adjacent vertices of v in order to IG ordering of intervals in the following way:

$$M_i(v) = \max \left\{ N[v] - \bigcup_{j=0}^{i-1} M_j(v) \right\}, \text{ with } M_0(v) = \max \{ N(v) \}$$

In connection with the highest numbered adjacent vertex of v , we call this $M_i(v)$ as the p -th numbered adjacent vertex of v . Let $u, v \in V$, if for some $i (i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, |N(v)|)$, $|N(v)| - i = p$ such that $u = M_i(v)$, then u is called the p -th numbered adjacent vertex of v .

1.4. ALGORITHM FOR DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATING SET OF AN INTERVAL GRAPH

Input: An interval graph $G=(V,E)$ with IG ordering vertex set $V=\{1,2,\dots,n\}$.

Output: Doubly Connected Dominating Set DCDS.

Step 1: Set $f(j)=0, \forall j=1,2,\dots, n$;

Step 2: Set $i=1, D=\phi$;

Step 2.1: Compute $W_i(f)=\sum_{v \in N[i]} f(v)$;

Step 2.2: If $W_i(f)=0$, then

Set $f(M_0(i))=1$ and $f(M_1(i))=1$;

take $DCDS = \{M_1(i)\}$;

Step 2.3: else if $W_i(f)=1$,

Step 2.3.1: if i is the last vertex, then take $f(M_0(i))=1$ and $f(M_1(i))=1$;

and also take $M_1(i)$ into DCDS

end if;

Step 2.3.2: if i is not the last vertex, then set $f(M_0(i))=1$ and $f(M_1(i))=1$;

and also take $M_0(i)$ into DCDS

end if;

Step 2.4: else if $W_i(f)=0$, i is the last vertex, then set

$f(M_1(i))=1$ and $f(M_2(i))=1$;

and also take $M_2(i)$ into DCDS

end if;

Step 2.5: else if $W_i(f) \geq 2$, then

DCDS remains unchanged;

end if;

Step 2.6: Calculate $i = i + 1$ and go to Step 2.1 and continue until the last

vertex;

end DCDS.

1.5. MAIN THEOREMS:

1.5.1. Theorem:

Let $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ be an n interval family and G is an interval graph corresponding to I . If v_1 and v_2 are any two intervals in I such that $v_2 \in \text{DCDS}$, where DCDS is a doubly connected dominating set, v_2 is not the first vertex. v_{2-1} intersects v_{2+1} . Then doubly connected domination occurs in G and the doubly connected domination number satisfies $\gamma_{DCR}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{cc}(G)}$, where $\gamma_{DCR}(G)$ is the Roman doubly connected domination number of the graph G .

Proof:

Let $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ be an n interval family and G is an interval graph corresponding to I . If v_1 and v_2 are any two intervals in I such that $v_2 \in \text{DCDS}$, where DCDS is a doubly connected dominating set. v_{2+1} must intersect v_2 and v_2 intersects v_{2-1} . If in case v_{2-1} not intersects v_{2+1} , then the graph V-DCDS was not connected and gives the contradiction for doubly connected domination. $|V_1| + 2|V_2|$ gives the Roman doubly connected domination number as it leads to the equality of $\gamma_{DCR}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{cc}(G)}$.

In this procedure we also find the doubly connected dominating set of an interval graph towards the algorithm as given in section 1.4 with an illustration.

1.5.2. Illustration:

The Interval graph G is as follows,

Fig.2: Interval graph G

Doubly connected dominating set $DCDS = \{v_2, v_4\}$

From the above interval graph G , the neighborhoods of each vertex are as follows,

$nbd [v_1] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3 \}$	$nbd [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 \}$
$nbd [v_3] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$	$nbd [v_4] = \{ v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$
$nbd [v_5] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$	

$M_i(v) \setminus v$	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5
$M_0(v)$	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_5	v_5
$M_1(v)$	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_4	v_4
$M_2(v)$	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_3	v_3
$M_3(v)$	-	v_1	v_2	v_2	-
$M_4(v)$	-	-	v_1	-	-
$M_5(v)$	-	-	-	-	-

To find the doubly connected dominating set, we have to compute all the p -th numbered adjacent vertices as above.

First set $f(j) = 0, \forall j \in V$. In step 2, set $i = 1$, $DCDS = \phi$, that is initially DCDS is empty. Step 2 repeats for n times. Here $n = 5$, the number of vertices in the interval graph G . We follow the iterations of the illustration through the table.

Iteration (1)

For the first iteration $i = 1$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_1] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3 \}$$

$$w_1(f) = f(N[v_1])$$

$$w_1(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3)$$

$$= 0 + 0 + 0 = 0$$

The first condition of if-end if is satisfied. Since $w_1(f) = 0$, we find $M_0(v_1) = v_3$ and $M_1(v_1) = v_2$. Then set

$$f(v_2) = 1 \text{ and } f(v_3) = 1$$

$$\text{Also set } DCDS = \phi \cup \{v_2\} \Rightarrow DCDS = \{v_2\}$$

Iteration (2)

For the second iteration $i = 2$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 \}$$

$$w_2(f) = f(N[v_2])$$

$$w_2(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4)$$

$$= 0 + 1 + 1 + 0 = 2$$

So, in this iteration DCDS could not be calculated. Hence DCDS remains same and i is being increased to 3.

Iteration (3)

For the third iteration $i = 3$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_3] = \{ \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \} \}$$

$$w_3(f) = f(\text{N}[v_3])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_3(f) &= f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) \\ &= 0 + 1 + 1 + 0 + 0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration DCDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 4.

Iteration (4)

For the fourth iteration $i = 4$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_4] = \{ \{ v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \} \}$$

$$w_4(f) = f(\text{N}[v_4])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_4(f) &= f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) \\ &= 1 + 1 + 0 + 0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration also DCDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 5.

Iteration (5)

For the fifth iteration $i = 5$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_5] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$$

$$w_5(f) = f(\text{N}[v_5])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_5(f) &= f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) \\ &= 1 + 0 + 0 = 1 \end{aligned}$$

We go to step 2.3.1, and take $M_1(v_5) = v_4$ into DCDS

$$DCDS = DCDS \cup \{v_4\} \Rightarrow DCDS = \{v_2, v_4\}$$

Now stop the iteration process as v_5 was the last vertex.

The cardinality of $DCDS = 2$ and the Roman doubly connected domination number is given as 4. As $DCDS = \{v_2, v_4\}$

$$\begin{aligned} |V_1| &= \{\emptyset\}, V_2 = \{v_2, v_4\} \\ \sum_{v \in V} f(v) &= |V_1| + 2|V_2| \\ &= 0 + 2 \cdot 2 = 4 \end{aligned}$$

satisfies $\gamma_{DCR}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{cc}(G)}$ Hence the theorem is proved.

1.5.3. Theorem:

Let G be an interval graph corresponding to an n interval family $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ If v_1 and v_2 are any two intervals in I such that v_2 belongs to $DCDS$ and intersects the last vertex in the interval family, then doubly connected domination occurs in G and the doubly connected domination number $\gamma_{cc}(G)$ satisfies the property $\gamma_{DCR}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{cc}(G)}$, where $\gamma_{DCR}(G)$ is the Roman doubly connected domination number of the graph G .

Proof:

Let G be an interval graph corresponding to an n interval family $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ If v_1 and v_2 are any two intervals in I such that v_2 belongs to $DCDS$ and intersects the last vertex in the interval family. If we take the first vertex into the $DCDS$, then it dominates every vertex in the interval family, as v_2 belongs to the $DCDS$ we can take the vertex v_{2+2} also into the $DCDS$ but not satisfies the algorithm properties as i is not the last vertex then we can take the vertex $M_0(v)$ into the $DCDS$.

We will find the doubly connected dominating set as follows from an interval graph using the algorithm as explained in section 1.4.

1.5.4. Illustration:

The interval graph G is as follows,

Fig.5: Interval graph G

The neighborhoods of each vertex from the above interval graph G are as follows,

$nbd [v_1] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3 \}$	$nbd [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_6 \}$
$nbd [v_3] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$	$nbd [v_4] = \{ v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$
$nbd [v_5] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$	$nbd [v_6] = \{ v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$

To find the doubly connected dominating set, we have to compute all the p -th numbered adjacent vertices as follows,

$M_i(v) \setminus v$	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_6
$M_0(v)$	v_3	v_6	v_5	v_6	v_6	v_6
$M_1(v)$	v_2	v_4	v_4	v_5	v_5	v_5
$M_2(v)$	v_1	v_3	v_3	v_4	v_4	v_4
$M_3(v)$	-	v_2	v_2	v_3	v_3	v_2
$M_4(v)$	-	v_1	v_1	v_2	-	-
$M_5(v)$	-	-	-	-	-	-

First set $f(j) = 0, \forall j \in V$. In step 2, set $i=1$, DCDS = ϕ , that is initially DCDS is empty. Step 2 repeats for n times. Here $n=6$ the number of vertices in the interval graph G . As follows the iterations through the table,

Iteration (1)

For the first iteration $i = 1$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_1] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3 \}$$

$$w_1(f) = f(N[v_1])$$

$$w_1(f) = f(v_1)+f(v_2)+ f(v_3)$$

$$= 0+0+0 = 0$$

The first condition of if-end if is satisfied. Since $w_1(f) = 0$, we find $M_0(v_1) = v_3$ and $M_1(v_1) = v_2$. Then set

$$f(v_2) = 1 \text{ and } f(v_3) = 1$$

$$\text{Also set } \text{DCDS} = \phi \cup \{v_2\} \Rightarrow \text{DCDS} = \{v_2\}$$

Iteration (2)

For the second iteration $i = 2$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_6 \}$$

$$w_2(f) = f(N[v_2])$$

$$w_2(f) = f(v_1)+f(v_2)+ f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+ f(v_6)$$

$$= 0+1+1+0+0 = 2$$

So, in this iteration DCDS could not be calculated. Hence DCDS remains same and i is being increased to 3.

Iteration (3):

For the third iteration $i = 3$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_3] = \{ \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \} \}$$

$$w_3(f) = f(\text{N}[v_3])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_3(f) &= f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) \\ &= 0 + 1 + 1 + 0 + 0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration DCDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 4.

Iteration (4):

For the fourth iteration $i = 4$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_4] = \{ v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$$

$$w_4(f) = f(\text{N}[v_4])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_4(f) &= f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) + f(v_6) \\ &= 1 + 1 + 0 + 0 + 0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration also DCDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 5.

Iteration (5):

For the fifth iteration $i = 5$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_5] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$$

$$w_5(f) = f(\text{N}[v_5])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_5(f) &= f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) + f(v_6) \\ &= 1 + 0 + 0 + 0 = 1 \end{aligned}$$

We go to step 2.3.2, and set $f(M_0(v_5)) = 1$, $f(M_1(v_5)) = 1$, take $M_0(v_5) = v_6$ into DCDS

$$\text{DCDS} = \text{DCDS} \cup \{v_6\} \Rightarrow \text{DCDS} = \{v_2, v_6\}$$

Now we go to the next iteration

Iteration (6):

For the sixth iteration $i = 6$

$$\text{Nbd}[v_6] = \{v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$$

$$w_6(f) = f(\text{N}[v_6])$$

$$w_6(f) = f(v_2) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) + f(v_6)$$

$$= 0 + 0 + 1 + 1 = 2$$

As v_6 was last vertex, it stops the iteration process here.

The cardinality of $\text{DCDS} = 2$ and the Roman doubly connected domination number is given as 4. As $\text{DCDS} = \{v_2, v_6\}$

$$|V_1| = \{\emptyset\}, V_2 = \{v_2, v_6\}$$

$$\sum_{v \in V} f(v) = |V_1| + 2|V_2|$$

$$= 0 + 2 \cdot 2 = 4$$

satisfies $\gamma_{DCR}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{cc}(G)}$ Hence the theorem is proved.

1.5.5. Theorem:

Let us consider an n interval family $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ and G be an interval graph of I . If v_1, v_2, v_3 are the first three intervals in the interval family and the third interval belongs to the DCDS and intersects the next vertex of the vertex which belongs to the DCDS, then doubly connected domination occurs in G with $\gamma_{DCR}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{cc}(G)}$, where $\gamma_{DCR}(G)$ is the

Roman doubly connected domination number of the graph G and $\gamma_{CC}(G)$ is the doubly connected domination number of the graph G .

Proof:

Let the family $I = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ be an n interval family and G be an interval graph of I . The third vertex intersects the next vertex of the vertex which belongs to the DCDS, it satisfies in the p -th numbered adjacent vertices table as by the algorithm, otherwise using the algorithm it was not the last iteration and gives the weight $w_i(f) = 1$, we have to take the last vertex into the DCDS and there was no connection for the third vertex of the interval family with the last vertex not satisfies the doubly connected domination. $|V_1| = \{\emptyset\}, |V_2| = 2, \sum_{v \in V} f(v) = |V_1| + 2|V_2|$, satisfies $\gamma_{DCR}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{CC}(G)}$. Now we will find the doubly connected dominating set using the algorithm as given in section 1.4 as follows,

1.5.6. Illustration:

The interval graph G is as follows,

Fig.8: Interval graph G

The corresponding neighborhoods of each vertex of the above interval graph G are as follows,

$nb\delta [v_1] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 \}$	$nb\delta [v_2] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 \}$
$nb\delta [v_3] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$	$nb\delta [v_4] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$
$nb\delta [v_5] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$	$nb\delta [v_6] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$
$nb\delta [v_7] = \{ v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$	

To find the doubly connected dominating set, we have to compute all the p -th numbered adjacent vertices as follows,

$M_i(v) \setminus v$	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_6	v_7
$M_0(v)$	v_4	v_5	v_6	v_6	v_7	v_7	v_7
$M_1(v)$	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_5	v_6	v_6	v_6
$M_2(v)$	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_4	v_5	v_5	v_5
$M_3(v)$	v_1	v_2	v_3	v_3	v_4	v_4	-
$M_4(v)$	-	v_1	v_2	v_2	v_3	v_3	-
$M_5(v)$	-	-	v_1	v_1	-	-	-

First set $f(j) = 0, \forall j \in V$. In step 2, set $i = 1$, $DCDS = \phi$, that is initially DCDS is empty. Step 2 repeats for n times. Here $n = 7$, the number of vertices in the interval graph G . As follows iterations,

Iteration (1)

For the first iteration $i = 1$

$$Nbd [v_1] = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$$

$$w_1(f) = f(N[v_1])$$

$$w_1(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4)$$

$$= 0+0+0+0 = 0$$

The first condition of if-end if is satisfied. Since $w_1(f) = 0$, we find $M_0(v_1) = v_4$ and $M_1(v_1) = v_3$. Then set

$$f(v_3) = 1 \text{ and } f(v_4) = 1$$

$$\text{Also set } DCDS = \phi \cup \{v_3\} \Rightarrow DCDS = \{v_3\}$$

Iteration (2)

For the second iteration $i = 2$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_2] = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5\}$$

$$w_2(f) = f(N[v_2])$$

$$w_2(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5)$$

$$= 0+0+1+1+0 = 2$$

So, in this iteration DCDS could not be calculated. Hence DCDS remains same and i is being increased to 3.

Iteration (3)

For the third iteration $i = 3$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_3] = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$$

$$w_3(f) = f(N[v_3])$$

$$w_3(f) = f(v_1) + f(v_2) + f(v_3) + f(v_4) + f(v_5) + f(v_6)$$

$$= 0+0+1+1+0+0 = 2$$

In this iteration DCDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 4.

Iteration (4)

For the fourth iteration $i = 4$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_4] = \{ v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6 \}$$

$$w_4(f) = f(N[v_4])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_4(f) &= f(v_1)+f(v_2)+ f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+f(v_5)+f(v_6) \\ &= 0+0+1+1+0+0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration also DCDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 5

Iteration (5)

For the fifth iteration $i = 5$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_5] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$$

$$w_5(f) = f(N[v_5])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_5(f) &= f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+f(v_5) +f(v_6) +f(v_7) \\ &= 1+1+0+0+0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this iteration also DCDS remains unchanged. The iteration number i is being increased to 6

Iteration (6)

For the sixth iteration $i = 6$

$$\text{Nbd } [v_6] = \{ v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 \}$$

$$w_6(f) = f(N[v_6])$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_6(f) &= f(v_3)+ f(v_4)+f(v_5) +f(v_6) +f(v_7) \\ &= 1+1+0+0+0 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

The iteration number i is being increased to 7.

Iteration (7)

For the seventh iteration $i = 7$

$$\text{Nbd}[v_7] = \{v_5, v_6, v_7\}$$

$$w_7(f) = f(N[v_6])$$

$$w_7(f) = f(v_5) + f(v_6) + f(v_7)$$

$$= 0+0+0 = 0$$

Go to step 2.4 and take $M_2(v_7)$ into the DCDS

$$\text{Therefore DCDS} = \{v_3, v_5\}$$

Thus it completes the iteration process and gives the final Doubly connected dominating set. satisfies $\gamma_{DCR}(G) = 2^{\gamma_{cc}(G)}$. Hence the theorem is proved.

REFERENCES:

- [1] E.J.Cockayne, S.T.Hedetniemi, Towards a theory of domination in graphs, Networks, Vol.7(1977), 247-261.
- [2] Cockayne, E.J. and Hedetniemi, S.T.- Towards a theory of domination in graphs, Networks, vol. 7. 1977, pp. 247-261.
- [3] Cockayne, E.J. Dreyer, P.A., Hedetniemi, S.M. and Hedetniemi, S.T.- Roman domination in graphs, Discrete math., vol. 278, 2003. Pp. 11- 22.
- [4] Ore O. – Theory of graphs, Amer, Math.Soc. Collaq. Publ.38, Providence (1962).
- [5] Berge, C. – Graphs and Hyperactive graphs, North Holland, Amsterdam in graphs, Networks, vol.10, 1980, pp.211-215.
- [6] Haynes, T.W., Hedetniemi, S.T. and Slater, P.J, - Domination in graphs, Advanced Topics, Marcel Dekkar, Inc., New Youk, 1998.
- [7] Haynes, T.W., Hedetniemi, S.T. and Slater, P>J. – Fundamentals of domination in graphs, Vol. 208 of Monographs and text books in pure and applied mathematics, marcel dekkar, new York, 1998.